

Paper 45

RESEARCH ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS WHATSAPP

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ABSTRACT

Today in rapidly moving world, we can see change in every moment. Therefore life is getting complicated in every phase but the technology has made life very convenient. It is evolving in the world at very fast pace and affecting people from various ways. And WhatsApp is one of the medium of such technology, now a days it is becoming a popular world among youth, which is currently available in the various electronic items such as I-Phone, Android, windows phone and computer also. WhatsApp is an amazing application, and with the help of it we can connect ourselves to the society and the whole world. It is an effective medium for the flow of information and ideas. This application is advantageous for us from many ways which occupies a major part of our day to day life. However, this app has emerged as an important medium for social networking and sharing of information and ideas even it has some harmful effect on the life of youth. Hence, it is essential to know how it is affecting the life of youth and the society at large. The present study is an attempt to study the impact of WhatsApp, with reference to youth of Agra, India. This empirical study has been conducted upon 100 respondents and an Interview schedule was used as tool of data collection.

Introduction

Since more than 20 years ago, the creation of SMS or short message were sent globally, highlighting that SMS is a mass communication medium used by billion of people around the globe. In recent times, however, a new wave of mobile communication services called mobile instant messaging applications have gained considerable momentum. Applications like WhatsApp, Viber and Line allow mobile users to send real time text messages to individuals or group of friends at one time and at no cost.

Today, one of the most interesting MM Application on the market is WhatsApp. WhatsApp is a platform of instant messaging application across the world for Smartphone. It enables

users to send and receive the location, information, images, video, audio and text messages in real time to individuals and group of friends at no cost.

Objectives

- The preliminary aim of the study is to examine the intensity of the usage of WhatsApp messenger among the youth of Andhra region.
- The major objective of this paper is to investigate the way, how it affects the education, psychology, routine life, family life and expenditure of the youth.
- The other objective of this paper is to evaluate the degree of positive and negative impact of WhatsApp messenger among youth.

Review of literature

WhatsApp is an application of social media therefore literary review of this paper can also be covered here with.

Social media can be defined as forms of electronic communication through which user can interact among people freely and can share, exchange and discuss the information, ideas, personal message and other content between each other such as using multimedia messages, personal words, pictures, video and audio, and utilizes online platform only by connecting to the internet.

They conducted a study to identify the issues regarding the youth's social networking usage and the resultant impact on their social interactions. The sample size was 150. The findings of the study include 98% number of people who are the members in social networking sites in which 68% are strangers, 7% are those who have very intimate relationship with their online friends and 20% are good friends with the virtual strangers. Thus it is a positive indication that Indian youth are not only techno-savvy and socially active, but they also possess social consciousness.

Hypothesis:

The intensity of usage of WhatsApp messenger is very high among youth because of its cheap cost.

WhatsApp messenger has negative impact on youth

Methodology

A strong methodology is the backbone of the research. It provides the ground to the research therefore the topic should also be selective. This research deals with Primary source and secondary source.

- Primary source

Standardized questionnaire used as primary source for the purpose of study. The questionnaire has both open ended and close ended questions.

- Secondary source

The following are the source for the study

Various research journals and periodicals

Various website on internet

Findings

1. Findings show a majority of youth about 72% joined WhatsApp because it is a good source of communication and youth can be in touch with their loved one through it. Apart from this it reduces expenditure also on calls and SMS.

2. The intensity of WhatsApp is very high in Agra region. The youth use WhatsApp 50 times in a day.

3. Moderate response about 48% reveals their favourite activities on WhatsApp are chatting, comedy and joking videos, and picture sharing.

4. A vast percentile of young generation about 63% visit WhatsApp 50 times in a day which is remarkable.

5. According to the survey, 40% of the sample respondents include only close friends in their WhatsApp list.

6. 47% out of the 68% studying youth strongly stated that WhatsApp occupies their studying time and is responsible for lot of grammatical mistakes, lack of concentration while lecturing. Thus it has negative effect on the study.

Conclusion

This paper investigates the impact of WhatsApp on youth in Agra. Therefore the study reveals considerable facts regarding youth and WhatsApp. However WhatsApp is much quicker and more convenient way to interact with people which enhance the effective flow of messages and ideas among youth. Indeed intensity of WhatsApp is very high among youth because it reduces calling and SMS costs. Therefore its primary objectives and hypothesis are evidently accepted.